

LEGAL AND CRIMINAL RESPONSIBILITIES OF INDEPENDENT ACCOUNTANT AND FINANCIAL ADVISORS

Ahmet ŞENGÜL*

To cite this article: Ahmet ŞENGÜL, Science, Volume 4, No. 12-3, 2022, p. 01 – 24. - 0099-0001-2212-0301.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("CURRENT SCIENCE - ResearchGate") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

*

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia")

- The magazine is published monthly.

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ABSTRACT

The independent accountant and financial advisors have responsibilities towards their taxpayers, employees, the state, investors, themselves and the public. Failure to perform this profession correctly affects the country's economy, market and future planning. For this reason, the legal rules and criminal

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

sanctions related to the accountancy profession should be known by both members of the profession, taxpayers and the society. This study aims to examine the legal and criminal responsibilities of the independent accountant and financial advisors. In order to realize this purpose, literature review, legislation review and case study research were conducted. As a result of the research, it has been concluded that legal regulations and sanctions should be constantly updated, audits and the awareness of responsibility in independent accountants and financial advisors should be increased. It is also concluded that the heaviest penalties are caused by professional carelessness.

Keywords: *Independent Accountant and Financial Advisor, Legal Responsibility, Criminal Responsibility, Sanction.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The accounting profession connects the organization, individuals and the government. Without accounting, employees, investors, partners and stakeholders would not have access to stable information. Similarly, these parties will not be able to make realistic future plans, set goals and develop loyalty to the organization. Accountancy implies accountability to the government, the organization and the people associated with the organization, as well as to society. It should be known that improperly placed accounting systems will bring problems in tax collection. This situation directly affects the social order and welfare. Because the basis of the economic policies of governments is the correct collection of taxes.

The accounting profession also serves the purpose of compiling the information required for strategic decision-making by all economic units. Accountancy provides many benefits such as the smooth continuation of a country's commercial activities with another country, investors' interest in the market, customers' trust in companies, employees' loyalty to their workplaces and the continuation of social peace.

Accountants must have developed conscientious judgment as well as the ability to make calculations. In addition, these people should be suitable for group work, know and understand the past and be able to make inferences for the future by looking at the past, and have strong communication skills. Professional technical knowledge is not enough to do justice to the accountancy profession. Professionals should also be able to improve themselves in ethical issues with unclear legal boundaries. They should follow innovations, select and use the most appropriate programs and continuously improve their timing skills. In this respect, accounting is one of the main units from which information, the most

important resource of the 21st century, originates. For these reasons, the profession of accountancy and financial advisor requires intensive training and awareness of the whole set of rules.

The main purpose of this study is to explain the responsibilities that will be incurred according to the relevant regulations if the accountancy is not performed in accordance with the law and to examine the legal, ethical and moral rules of the profession. In line with this purpose, the general framework of the profession of independent accountant and financial advisor is drawn in the second section following the Introduction. In this context, the conditions required for the fulfillment of the accountancy profession and the role of the accountancy profession in crime prevention are examined.

The third part of the study includes a literature review on the subject.

In the fourth part of the study, the legal and criminal responsibilities of independent accountant financial advisors are analyzed within the framework of the decisions of the disciplinary board of the Chamber of Certified Public Accountants of Istanbul

In the last part of the study titled "Conclusion", the conclusions reached on the subject are given.

2. GENERAL FRAMEWORK OF THE PROFESSION OF INDEPENDENT ACCOUNTANT AND FINANCIAL ADVISOR

2.1. Basic Duties of Independent Accountant and Financial Advisors

Accountants and financial advisors are self-employed professionals who, upon the request of business managers and the government, certify that the financial statements prepared by the business "accurately reflect the facts of the business in a complete and honest manner in accordance with accounting principles and rules" (Yildiz, 1998, p.6).

Accounting is the system that allows economic relations to be managed and recorded. For this reason, it is a field that has existed continuously since the early ages and has continued to develop continuously. Especially globalization and easy access to the market have started to create a great competitive pressure on businesses and this has increased the number of negative behaviors such as reducing costs and wanting to avoid tax responsibility. Today, the responsibility on accountants is much higher. Accountants and businesses that do not know how to behave ethically can easily resort to fraud and this situation has a negative impact on the economy of the business, employees, investors, competitors and the country's economy. For this reason, the most important duty of the accountant is primarily to observe the public interest and to be honest. Thanks to accounting, the management of enterprises can realize strategic plans. Thanks to this feature, the accounting profession actually undertakes the task of management support (Ahid & Augustine, 2012, p.44).

Today, the ability to use the right sources of information lies at the heart of the success of businesses and even country administrations. It is seen that people act according to their past experiences while planning for their future. Accounting aims to display past information in a systematic way and thus enables the most correct future planning. Accounting is the only department that is directly connected with the management units of enterprises. The reports prepared by accounting allow the management to see which units are performing and to what extent and constitute a natural internal control mechanism for many activities such as business execution, time and resource management, production, sales, human resources (Mojgan, 2012, p.2). All these can be counted among the important invisible tasks of the accounting profession.

2.2. History of Financial Advisory

Studying the history of accounting is important for shedding light on how today's economic conditions were achieved and how relationships, especially between governments, were shaped by financial systems. Accounting records can be the key to learning about the legal structure and commercial relations of the relevant period and even women's rights (Gomes, Carnegie, Napier, Parker, & West, 2011, p.389). The rapid development of accounting has been due to developments such as the increasing importance of the private sector and management sciences and the efforts of businesses to reduce costs to make themselves stronger in the competitive environment (Carmona, Ezzamel, & Gutierrez, 2004, p.27).

The fact that people started to exchange with each other and then these relationships formed the economy, led to the need to calculate and record them. According to some sources, accounting emerged as a profession in England in the 19th century. However, it should be noted that accounting has developed from Babylon and Egypt to the present day. Since the commercial relations of people with each other would be healthier with an impartial unit balancing this relationship as an intermediary, ancient accountants emerged. In 652, the first Islamic accounting systems began to form. Historical studies show that accounting records began to be kept in Mecca since 610. Until 622, the constant religious wars in the Arabian Peninsula caused the accounting records and the standards of accounting at that time to change constantly. Afterwards, the Prophet Muhammad began to cite Qur'anic verses in relation to accounting and the Qur'anic provisions began to be used in commercial exchanges between people. After 652, the first Muslim schools started to be opened on what accounting is and how it should be done (Ambashe and Alrawi, 2013, p.97).

According to another source, the foundations of modern accounting were laid in Venice in the 16th century with the development of mercantilism. Business operators of the period began to employ individuals who knew how to calculate in order to record financial transactions and keep them under constant control. In the 18th century, developed countries such as England, France, the US and Germany

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

began to carry out accounting in an organized manner, which enabled the rapid economic development of these countries. In 1972, the National Society of Accountants established the first institute for management accounting in the US. In this way, accounting started to be used in managerial processes as well as for government and tax calculations. Following these developments, accountancy was divided into sub-specialties such as certified management accountancy (Yıldız, 1998, p.6-7).

During the reign of Sultan Mehmet, the Conqueror, the first laws on accounting were enacted in the Ottoman Empire. Islamic rules were the main factor that shaped Ottoman accounting. The most important accounting records are found in the population and land survey books. Thanks to these books, the personal assets and security of the people as well as the amounts of taxes were determined. These books contained detailed information such as the land in the villages, which lands were cultivated, which products were extracted, the occupations of the population, and the number of men. This information was of great importance for the centralized administration of the state with vast territories (Can and Esen, 2010, p.2-3).

The establishment of various standards in accounting in Turkey was realized with the influence of German academicians who came to our country between 1926 and 1960. However, it was possible for it to take its modern form in 1980 and afterwards. The modern accountancy profession in Turkey gained its legal structure with the Law No. 3568 on Independent Accountant and Financial Advisor and Sworn-in Certified Public Accountants. With this law, the accountancy profession was classified as narrow (independent accountants) and broad (independent accountants and financial advisors and sworn-in certified public accountants). Afterwards, relevant schools started to be opened in order to perform the accountancy profession according to various standards (Yıldız, 1998, p.7).

2.3. The Profession of Independent Accountant and Financial Advisor

Accountants are people who examine the financial activities of an organization, inside or outside the business, turn them into tables and produce information about these transactions. Accounting information is vital for the future of businesses. Incorrect calculations, scandals or unusual situations that arise in accounting can create problems that can cause businesses to disappear. Accurate realization and interpretation of financial activities are essential for businesses to continue to exist and to fulfill their responsibilities to their employees, customers, suppliers, stakeholders, society and the government. At this point, accounting units come into play (Demir, 2013, p.228).

The accountancy profession is a constantly evolving profession. For this reason, it is also very difficult to define and the person practicing this profession must have knowledge in subjects such as law, economics, finance and technology (Diyaroğlu, 2010, p.25).

Accounting should not be perceived only as the tabulation of inputs and outputs. Information, which is the building block of strategic management, is obtained through accounting and plans for the

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

future are made in line with the information received. Accountants are responsible not only to their taxpayers and the government, but also to their taxpayers' employees and families, investors, customers, business partners and even the global economy. Accountancy is a profession in which the ability to be ethical and moral as well as accurate accounting is highly felt. Thanks to the accounting profession, an auditing mechanism is formed in the business environment. In addition, markets are determined and the economic conditions of the business and the region and country where that business is located are distinguished. Thanks to the data flowing from accounting, it is possible to understand important strategic elements such as benefits, losses, costs, capacity, productivity and efficiency, as well as investment planning for the future in both companies and the country (Mojgan, 2012, p.2).

Accounting is a profession that requires attention and is based on the ability to follow and calculate. For this reason, no matter which type of accounting is performed, the mental qualities of the person are of great importance. The person should have the ability to think analytically, interpret tables and graphs and prepare them. Communication skills are also important in terms of doing the accounting job correctly and especially in helping business managers to make decisions. The accounting officer who interprets the available data should be able to talk about them in an enlightening way with decision makers.

It is also very important that the accountant is impartial and follows ethical rules. This profession is complex and requires an intense pace of work. The accountant should be able to analyze the problems that seem complex and should be able to correctly prioritize the importance of the solution (Diyaroğlu, 2010, pp.27-29).

Accounting has the function of providing the business and all parties related to the business with the information they need. Therefore, it is very important that accountants have good communication skills. Although there are various standards for financial statements and reports, the accountant's ability to explain what they do is vital for the correct flow of information. In addition, it is important for the professional to communicate correctly with the employees working with him/her in terms of the correct progress of the work (Özyürek, 2012, p.142).

In order to be able to work as an accountant, it is necessary to have successfully graduated from an educational institution that provides technical knowledge. Experience and research are among the other factors that increase professional qualifications. In addition, there is also the requirement that members of the profession must not have been subjected to certain penalties. Article 4 of Law No. 3568 states that individuals who will work in the accountancy profession must not have been sentenced to heavy imprisonment or imprisonment for more than five years. In addition, they must not have been convicted of disgraceful crimes such as embezzlement, collusion, extortion, bribery, theft, fraud,

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

forgery, abuse of faith, fraudulent bankruptcy, conspiracy to rig official tenders and purchases and sales, revealing state secrets, tax evasion or attempted tax evasion (Özyürek, 2012, p.142).

2.4. The Role of Independent Accountant and Financial Advisors in Preventing Crimes

The most important duties of independent accountants and financial advisors are to control the income and expenses of companies. However, individuals with this profession have duties towards the government as well as the businesses they work with. These individuals also play a key role in collecting taxes, the most important source of income for the government. Individuals belonging to this profession work for the government to collect taxes on time and in full. For this reason, when it comes to financial advisors and independent accountants and their responsibilities, tax responsibility comes to mind first (Çürük & Tüm, 2011, p.59).

However, the only responsibility of accountants is of course not the collection of taxes. As a result of the transactions made by accounting, the profit and loss rates of the enterprises are determined and the decision makers of their organizations make their future planning by taking into account the calculation results of accountants and financial advisors. For this reason, the accounting profession is developing day by day thanks to technological developments and economic cooperation in the world (Yıldız, 2010, p.156).

Financial advisors also have an important role in ensuring that organizations provide social benefits. In order for businesses to fulfill their social responsibilities and their responsibilities towards their stakeholders and employees, accounting accounts should be done correctly and the financial situation of the company should be routinely controlled. The image of an enterprise is directly related to what it brings to society and its ability to fulfill its duties, and damage to the image may mean the collapse of the enterprise in a short time. Accounting is the language of businesses. Their fulfillment of their duties is vital for the survival of the organization (Tilt, 2009, p. 12).

Accountants are the people who can easily see the financial mistakes and frauds made in the business. The most important reason for this is that all relevant documents are constantly monitored by accountants. This is an indication that accountants have a great responsibility (Yılmaz & Kaya, 2014, p.31). Accountants should be fair, transparent, accountable and responsible.

When the words accounting and crime are used at the same time, the concept of fraud usually comes to mind. Although it is thought that fraud will provide various contributions to the operators, it should not be forgotten that it will definitely be revealed after a while. At this point, it is necessary to mention the fraud triangle. The fraud triangle is used to describe the conditions that allow crimes to be committed in an environment where accounting transactions are made. In the fraud triangle, which was

first discussed by sociologist Donald Cressey, the desire to transfer money to one's own embezzlement and the conditions that force the individual to cheat are discussed. Cressey argues that the fraud triangle must be completed for fraud to occur (Akalın, 2017, p.24).

Although Cressey argues that the elements of opportunity, pressure and justification must be together for fraud to occur, SAS No.99 (Statement on Auditing Standards No. 99) is of the opinion that the existence of any of the parties forming this triangle is sufficient for fraud to occur (Küçük & Uzay, 2009, p.3). However, according to SAS, if all three conditions are present, there is fraud. SAS explains these three factors as follows (Karavardar, 2015, p.29).

i. Pressure: When management or employees are under pressure for some reason, they may make fraud. For example, many variables such as the deterioration of economic balances in the market, the need for cash, livelihood problems, goals to be achieved, the political situation, etc. can make managers and therefore employees or only employees feel under pressure.

ii. Opportunity: Lack of adequate controls inside and outside the organization creates a favorable environment for people to make fraud.

iii. Justification: When a person feels justified in the face of his/her crime, he/she will feel comfortable to make fraud. For example, pressure from the management may lead the individual to make fraud by feeling justified. In addition, situations such as livelihood problems, salary or inequality of opportunity will trigger the desire to increase one's own comfort.

Breaking the fraud triangle by the government and businesses means disrupting the favorable environment for fraud. For this reason, businesses should first find and improve their weak points, prove internal control systems and set the right goals for the future. Accountants have a key role in setting the right targets and creating control mechanisms (Küçük & Uzay, 2009, p.5; Karavardar, 2015, p.29).

The unfair use of title and oath has an important share in the realization of the element of fraud. Obtaining an oath or title is the result of a certain accumulation and effort. In the accountancy profession, education and experience are needed to obtain them. Using the title or oath unfairly means betraying one's own efforts. As in every profession, both ethically and morally and legally, it is forbidden to use the titles used for the profession and the oaths that give the responsibility to perform that profession within the framework of the law. In fact, according to Article 3 of Law No. 3568, *"The employment of the titles of "Certified Public Accountant", and "Sworn-in Certified Public Accountant" by individuals legally unauthorized, and the employment of titles, signs and symbols simulating the said professional titles, or likely to cause erroneous identification, are prohibited"*. This situation protects the taxpayers and prevents the misunderstandings they may fall into. The unfair use of oaths and titles prevents both the efforts of the members of the profession who have worked to obtain them and the deception of customers, the public, partners and investors (Karakaş, 2016, p.25).

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

Certification procedures represent another area where unlawful transactions may find grounds. Sworn-in certified public accountants verify the authenticity of various documents, which indicates that they are responsible for the certification process. The relationship between the CPA and the taxpayer starts with a contract. The contract guarantees that a work is carried out, that this work is carried out for the benefit of the client, and that accounting transactions and tax audits are carried out at appropriate times. On the other hand, the sworn-in certified public accountants may violate the contract intentionally or due to various mistakes, and damages may occur due to this violation. Sworn-in certified public accountants are held responsible for the damages arising from breaches. In case of breaches, it should be kept in mind that the damage will be both material and moral. Of course, it is not possible to place the burden of all errors on the relevant consultant. At this point, it is necessary to explain what a defect is. The fact that the relevant advisor fails to do so when it has the chance to prevent the error and desires an unlawful result summarizes the defect (Çürük & Tüm, 2011, pp.62-63; Kepekçi, 1995, p.256).

Another area where unlawfulness in accounting transactions may be observed is related to the keeping of professional secrets. Confidentiality is one of the concepts of professional ethics in accounting within the AICPA Code of Professional Conduct. In addition, Article 43 of Law No. 3568 includes regulations on professional secrets (İşgüden and Çabuk, 2006, pp.70-71). The purpose of the accounting profession is to examine, record, inform and interpret the financial movements of the enterprise. In this way, while making plans for the financial future of the enterprise, responsibilities towards the society, employees and the government are also fulfilled. However, the person who deals with accounting has a lot of information about the business that is the customer over time. Disseminating this information without the client's knowledge and permission would not comply with the rules of professional ethics and is contrary to accounting standards. The information and documents obtained during the studies are classified as confidential documents. However, at this point, it should be noted that the documents that accountants should share with the public and relevant units are excluded from the subject. *"According to the concept of full disclosure, which is one of the basic concepts of accounting, mandatory disclosures that must be made in accordance with the audit rules and disclosures required by law for public disclosure purposes are not considered confidential"* (Okay, 2011, p.31).

Law No. 3568 strictly prohibits those practicing the accounting profession from disseminating the information obtained about the business, while underlining that situations that constitute a crime should be announced to the competent authorities. In fact, at this point, confidentiality is intertwined with the principle of impartiality in the profession. The accounting officer should be independent, should fulfill his/her profession honestly without being under pressure from anyone, and in case of error or fraud, he/she should inform the necessary authorities about the situation instead of helping it (Yılmaz & Kaya, 2014, p.25).

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

2.5. Forensic Accounting

Forensic accountants are one of the most important bodies to identify accounting errors, fraud and criminal liabilities and to apply the right sanctions to those responsible before the law. Bekçioğlu, Coşkun and Gümüş (2013: 3) defines the word forensic as "subject to court or public discussions; related to or used in these discussions". Forensic accounting is used to identify situations that give rise to suspicion of crime related to accounting. According to some authors, forensic accounting is an old phenomenon dating back to Egyptian civilizations. However, its use in the judiciary is quite new. Especially the increase in transnational or international businesses has led to the need for new disciplines to combat corruption.

Forensic accounting is carried out by forensic accountants and these people should have an investigative structure. In addition, these people should have completed their education in accounting, litigation services and criminology (Dönmez & Çavuşoğlu, 2015, p.51). The working areas of forensic accounting are quite wide. Accounting and forensic accounting are concepts that differ from each other at this point. While in accountancy, works related to numbers are generally carried out, in forensic accounting, in addition to numbers, disciplines based on human factors such as psychology, sociology and law are also worked with. The main purpose of this profession is to assist judicial decision-makers (Bekçioğlu et al., 2013, p.4). To achieve this, forensic accountants carry out one or more of the following activities: litigation support, expert witness and fraud investigation.

Litigation support is a service provided to lawyers before or during the course of a lawsuit and is mostly used to help identify economic losses. It includes activities such as compiling the necessary documents to refute or support the allegations, reviewing documents to assess the situation, identifying missing points if there are any, expressing an opinion on the outcome of the case and expressing an opinion on its conclusion, and attending the hearing (Saçaklı, 2011, p.53).

The forensic accountant collects the necessary documents and evidence and provides instructive information to the parties and judges during the litigation process. When an expert opinion is needed in the field of accounting, support can be obtained from an impartial forensic accountant. This effectiveness of forensic accounting is of great importance, especially for the courts to make the right decision in criminal transactions that are under the responsibility of accounting (Çankaya & Gerekan, 2009, p.96).

Fraud investigation is also known as fraud auditing. Individuals or groups at all levels in businesses can apply to the fraud investigation of forensic accountants. Activities such as detecting frauds or accounting crimes committed by business employees, examining bank transactions, analyzing

investments and detecting fraud, financial statement changes applied by managers for business image are carried out under the title of fraud investigation (Saçaklı, 2011, p.54).

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Businesses are the basic elements that ensure the existence of the economy. Production and consumption is a necessary cycle and this cycle will exist as long as people exist. Accounting is a science that is essential for businesses to have relations with the public, the government and other businesses. Since a business can be trusted by looking at accounting information, many activities such as taxes collected for public benefit, investments made, working in a workplace, becoming a partner, giving up partnership are decided. It is vital for economic continuity that these activities are based on real information.

A review of the literature reveals that there are many studies on the responsibilities of accounting professionals. However, academic studies have examined the responsibilities of accountants on certain issues rather than all of their responsibilities.

Çitil (2013, p.345) addresses the responsibilities of accountants in tax law and examines the rules that accountants should comply with based on the legislation regulating these responsibilities. The author explains the responsibilities of accountants as follows: "The responsibility of financial advisors in tax law is regulated in the repeated Article 227 of the Law No. 213 and the principle that financial advisors will be held jointly and severally liable together with the taxpayer for the tax, penalty and default interest due to the defective fulfillment of their formal duties". The researcher underlines that the law holds accountants equally responsible with tax debtors.

Çürük and Tüm (2011, pp.73- 74) examines the concept of responsibility in the accountancy profession with a special focus on Sworn-in Certified Public Accountants (SCPAs). The researchers first examined the responsibilities of SCPAs in the theoretical framework and then conducted a survey with the members of the profession regarding the problems that arise in case these responsibilities are not fulfilled. According to the research, there should be detailed regulations in the Tax Procedure Law (TPL) regarding the point at which the responsibilities of SCPAs arise and what exactly their limits are. The researchers state that there are contradictions between the Law No. 3568 on the responsibilities of the SCPAs and the repeated Article 227 of the Tax Procedure Law. They stated that the joint and several liability arising jointly and severally with the taxpayer due to the inaccuracy of the certification process performed by the SCPAs should be redefined.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Diyaroğlu (2010, pp.116-118) mentions that accountants may make mistakes in matters such as recording, reporting, auditing and calculation. Underlining that because of these mistakes, businesses and responsible accountants may be exposed to millions of liras of losses, the researcher states that Professional Liability Insurance for Accountants and Financial Advisors is made to prevent major damages. As a result of his study, the author concludes that the premiums of Professional Liability Insurance are extremely high, individuals with and without realized risks come together in this system, moral weaknesses increase with these insurance systems and cause asymmetric information problems.

Çalış and Altınsoy (2014, p.43) investigated the responsibilities of accountants in internal audit and control systems. In the study, it was seen that the internal control system had benefits such as prompt intervention to accounting errors, correct future planning and reference when making decisions. The authors state that in internal control mechanisms, responsibility is usually evaluated in terms of processes related to the business, while in accounting, the area of responsibility is widened even if the audit is within the business. Research has also shown that responsible behavior in accounting and the maintenance of functional control mechanisms result in significant reductions in operating expenses. For example, when the budgets and actual labor costs of the company where an internal control system was implemented were compared, it was revealed that a 29% gain was achieved in terms of labor costs.

Ulusoy (2007, pp.140- 141) states that one of the most important responsibilities of accountants is to the investment markets. People make their investments by seeing the information provided by accounting. But of course, fraud and errors concern not only the markets and investors, but also many other segments such as the government, employees, and lenders through them. As a result of the study, the researcher has listed the factors necessary for the prevention and easy detection of errors and fraud. Accordingly, the objectivity, professional competence and level of responsibility of the persons responsible for the preparation of financial statements were found to be the primary important factors. In addition, the importance of accounting procedures and auditing guidelines and legal limitations recommended by the accounting authorities on transparency was emphasized. It is also stated that the routine and sometimes even unannounced independent audit is the most important point that prevents the entity from making mistakes. In addition to all these, it is also emphasized that the realization of recording systems by making use of technology, the creation of an organizational culture, the development of awareness about professional ethics, and the awareness of employees about their responsibilities and criminal sanctions are other important tools to prevent errors and fraud.

Şişmanoğlu (2016, p.180) investigates the impact of auditors' personal judgment and ethical understanding on auditing. The author states that many factors such as an individual's beliefs, professional knowledge, understanding of responsibility and culture play a role in developing and expressing opinions. The researcher underlines that professional judgment is not formed solely by

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

education, that there is no standardization in the factors that shape it, and that the effects of this situation on accounting responsibility will be variable.

Küçük and Uzay (2009, p.1) examine the consequences of accounting fraud in a multidimensional way and draw attention to the consequences of accounting scandals that can lead to the bankruptcy of a company and even the loss of confidence in a country's market. Researchers emphasize that fraudulent accounting indicators do not only concern the individuals concerned, that it is not enough for these individuals to be punished before the law, and that everyone should work in some way to see and prevent fraud. The researchers argue that fraud is a situation that deeply affects not only an individual or an organization, but also macroeconomic actors, and that laws and governments should focus on solving the root causes of fraud.

Okay (2011, p.110) discusses accounting errors and frauds in terms of professional ethics. The researcher argues that especially frauds are made with the hope of gaining prestige at the global level. The ever-growing interest and profit expectation of the groups interested in businesses sometimes pushes businesses to fraud. In order not to lose their shareholders and not to damage the trust of their customers, businesses sometimes make changes in their financial statements that increase their image. According to the researcher, this situation is becoming a natural consequence of global economic relations. The researcher argues that investors and governments should increase their scrutiny of financial statements and do so more carefully in order to avoid negative surprises. In the light of changing economic relations and technological developments, the author argues that the legislation is outdated and that more time should be devoted to ethics in professional trainings as well as tightening legal sanctions in order to train reliable market elements. Especially professional organizations have a lot of work to do in this regard. In order to avoid fraud, social sanctions are also necessary. It is important that the person knows that he/she will not only be afraid of legal penalties, but also that when he/she behaves unethically, he/she will be pushed by the society and lose friendships. This is possible by strengthening social awareness.

Karavardar (2015, p.42), who studies when, for what and in what ways people make fraud and how to detect them, examines the anatomy of fraud. The author states that by utilizing statistical information and mathematical calculations about the factors that make up the frauds, " fraud discriminator software" can be made that can be observed from inside or outside the business. It is essential for a person to justify himself/herself to make fraud and to have the opportunity to do so. In addition to minimizing opportunities, working with human resources to develop software scenarios to detect people with the potential to fraud is the most technological way to implement high security measures. The author underlines that auditors should also pay attention to the existence of the elements that constitute fraud in order to detect fraud. In fact, accurate observation is a very easy, inexpensive

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

and simple method to ensure that fraud can be prevented. In order to uncover accounting fraud, it is necessary to observe the environments in which the factors that cause fraud exist. For example, a person or organization in serious debt may want to resort to fraud. Psychological reasons such as ambitions, anxiety, intensity of competition and pressure may push people to fraud. With the correct observation of human resources, it will be possible to eliminate fraud opportunities.

Savaşan (2006, p. 41) analyzes the issue in terms of tax amnesties. The author states that businesses that owe taxes due to mistakes or frauds or delayed tax payments, especially in developing countries, get rid of this problem thanks to frequent tax amnesties and lists the benefits of amnesties in terms of collective money inflow to the state and reducing the burden of courts. However, the researcher draws attention to another phenomenon. Due to the expectation of amnesty, some businesses may deliberately delay paying their taxes or resort to various frauds in their financial statements. Amnesties are legal practices that have both pros and cons. Frequent amnesties may negatively affect tax compliance. The fact that there are serious criticisms about tax amnesties, especially in developed countries, should draw the attention of developing countries such as Turkey. Amnesties may allow businesses and individuals to avoid their responsibilities and increase the risk of errors and fraud.

Köse and Ertan (2016, p. 305) approaches the responsibility of accountancy from the audit side. Individuals related to accounting who are authorized to perform audits have the responsibility to provide accurate information first and foremost. In all accounting audit systems, internal and external, the results should be reflected accurately and as they are. The author emphasizes the importance of accountants and auditors to provide accurate information in economic life and reminds the regulations regarding the legal responsibilities of auditors in case of detection of accounting fraud. In particular, according to the Turkish Commercial Code, those who have an auditing role are criminally liable if they do not do what is necessary in case of detection of fraud or if they do not act in accordance with the standards during the audit.

4. EXAMINATION OF THE LEGAL AND CRIMINAL RESPONSIBILITIES OF INDEPENDENT ACCOUNTANT AND FINANCIAL ADVISORS WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE DECISIONS OF THE DISCIPLINARY BOARD OF THE CHAMBER OF CERTIFIED PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS OF ISTANBUL

Under this heading, the decisions of the disciplinary board of the Chamber of Certified Public Accountants of Istanbul (CCPAI) on various dates are analyzed in order to clearly understand the legal and criminal responsibilities imposed by the professional rules on the members of the profession.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

The subject of the first decision is related to the unfair competition created by a member of the accounting profession in violation of the professional rules and the Regulation on the Working Procedures and Principles of Law No. 3568. Within the scope of the relevant decision, it is understood that the advertisement of a person who has been a member of the profession for 30 years was published on a website, another member of the profession came across the advertisement and complained about it, as a result of which the Unfair Competition Board took the defense of the member of the profession and referred him to the disciplinary board. In the advertisement placed on the website, the professional member stated that he could "buy an accounting ledger in return for a percentage" and this was considered as an advertisement. In his defense, the professional stated that he did not even remember the advertisement and the website. In addition, the professional stated that he was already at retirement age and that he would ask for "as many taxpayers as he could take care of" instead of competing. The professional accepted that it was a publication, but stated that he did not submit it himself and that the advertisement was removed after the Competition Board's contact. In return, it was decided that there was no need for disciplinary action since there was no concrete information and documentation regarding the alleged action.

This decision should be taken as an indication of the importance of every word written in electronic media in the accountancy profession. Members of the profession should meticulously avoid any action that may be perceived as an element of unfair competition. The relevant professional member did not deny the existence of the advertisement, but stated that he did not make it. Although the relevant person should be disciplined pursuant to Article 7 of the Regulation, CCPAI did not deem it necessary.

Another decision concerns non-compliance with the Regulation on Working Procedures and Principles of Law No. 3568 and the suspicion of non-compliance with accounting and auditing standards and lack of due professional care in the conduct of professional activities. A complaint was filed against the professional member on the grounds that he did not deliver the books and other documents to the taxpayer whose contract was canceled within the required time. The complainant taxpayer added to the complaint that the address of the professional member was not up to date and therefore he could not send a notice to him. Upon this, the Chamber Secretariat sent an invitation to the professional member to evaluate his views and to receive his defense. The professional member's failure to appear upon this invitation caused the matter to turn into a disciplinary proceeding with the Commission Report. The professional member declared that the allegations were unfounded, that he had terminated his business relationship with his client, and that he had submitted all documents that he was required to submit within the required dates, and submitted documents proving this. As a result, it was decided that there was no need to discipline the professional.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

This decision shows that customers can easily complain to the Chamber if they experience various problems with members of the profession and that all complaints are taken seriously. The Chamber evaluates all kinds of complaints and initiates an investigation. Another important point of the decision is that it once again emphasizes the importance of record keeping in the accounting profession. The fact that the accounting professional has a record of submitting the relevant documents at the right place and time has enabled him to continue his profession without any problems.

Another decision is related to the allegation that the members of the profession deliberately violated the principles and rules in the legal regulations and the announced norms and standards regarding the signing and auditing of declarations and notifications, or deliberately used the authority to sign and audit declarations in violation of the truth. During the investigation, it was determined that there was no employment contract between the relevant professional member and the taxpayer, and that the professional member filled in the taxpayer's declarations several times with his own password. Upon this information, the professional member was asked how the taxpayer accessed and used his own password. Upon this, the professional member stated that the taxpayer's information was brought by a third party and that he did not see the taxpayer's documents. Stating that his relationship with the accounting profession ended when the taxpayer got into trouble with the financial police, the professional member stated that he was accused of being involved in an unlawful process, but that he had no knowledge or relationship with the matter.

During the examinations, it was observed that the taxpayer's company, which is the subject of the decision, had no activities. The taxpayer established his company for the purpose of trading forged documents. It was understood that the professional member did not know the taxpayer, had never met him, and did not fill out the declarations himself. In addition, it was determined that although the password of the professional member was used, his name was not used. The professional member claimed that he did not give his password and that it was used by someone else without his knowledge and permission. During the examination process, the accuracy of the allegations was investigated from VDINTRA and it was determined that the taxpayer's declarations were entered by someone else. As a result, it was decided to temporarily (12 months) suspend the relevant professional member from work.

In this decision, a single act violates more than one rule. The professional member did not take care of the password entrusted to him, performed work without a contract and employed people who were not related to the profession. The most important reason for the penalty is that the intermediary between the taxpayer and the professional is not an accountant. In addition, it is also determined by laws and regulations that all of the work of the professional member is under his/her own responsibility. The professional is held responsible for all kinds of transactions, even if he/she did not perform them himself/herself. In his statement, the professional said that he did not know the client at all and that the

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

declaration of this client was brought to him for a fee through someone else. This constitutes unfair competition in relations with business owners. This decision is an important example of what kind of criminal responsibilities the members of the accountancy profession will be under as a result of the use of their licenses and authorities by others.

Another decision examined covers issues such as the professional member's failure to provide information on change of address, non-receipt of documents sent to the professional member, and the professional member continuing to practice his profession despite having been suspended from the profession due to previous offenses. The professional has previously been suspended from the profession for more than 6 months and received numerous reprimands. In addition, various accusations were made against him, such as not paying due diligence to the profession, not being careful when signing the declaration, not reporting the declaration with the correct information at the right time. The professional was called to defend himself against these accusations, but he did not receive the notices. Afterwards, an attempt was made to reach him through a newspaper advertisement, but he still did not make a defense. Therefore, the decision was rendered in absentia. As a result, it was determined that the professional member acted in violation of professional norms and standards while providing services. Since the professional was previously reprimanded for a similar offense, CCPAI imposed a 6-month suspension from the profession.

The most important point of this decision is that the accusations against the professional members were evaluated separately. The previous offenses of the professional member were handled differently from each other and penalties of reprimand or suspension from the profession were given according to the necessity of the offense. However, it is also seen that the penalty is aggravated with the repetition of the offense.

In another decision, charges were brought against the professional member on grounds such as not complying with accounting and auditing standards, failing to exercise due professional care in the conduct of professional activities, issuing and certifying false documents in a way to mislead third parties, deliberately violating the principles and rules in the legal regulations regarding the signing and auditing of declarations and notifications, or deliberately using the declaration and audit authority falsely. Within the scope of this decision, it is seen that the professional member was notified of the accusations but could not be reached, and then the person was called through a newspaper announcement, but still did not come for defense. Therefore, pursuant to Article 23 of the Disciplinary Regulation, the decision was made in absentia. In the aforementioned decision, the professional member was accused of not showing sufficient care in a taxpayer declaration prepared by him. Reports were prepared on the matter, but the professional member could not be reached during the preparation of the report. Therefore, it was deemed appropriate to impose a reprimand penalty on the professional member.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

The most important point of this decision is that even in important matters such as lack of professional diligence, members of the profession are given the right to defend themselves before disciplinary proceedings are taken. In the file examined, it is understood that although the professional member had changed his/her address, he/she did not inform about it. This situation is actually a crime. However, the inability to reach the accountant is excluded from the scope of this decision. This is an indication that the issues are not confused and criminal liability is evaluated separately for each negative behavior.

Another decision concerns a professional's failure to appear for the defense in relation to the accusations against him. One of the professional's taxpayers was accused of being a forged business, and it was determined that this company had the sole purpose of issuing forged documents. The accountant of a company whose real objective is not to carry out commercial activities is also responsible for this. The documents issued by the accountant and the company are within the scope of forged documents according to Article 359 of Law No. 213. This situation subject to the decision was asked to the professional member via MERNIS and he was asked to provide information. After the examinations, it was seen that all declarations and notifications of the company subject to the decision were made by the professional member. Thereupon, the professional member was called for defense again, but he did not respond to the invitation. As a result, it was determined that the professional member did not give due importance to his profession and did not act meticulously enough during his work. Thereupon, according to Article 6/n of the Disciplinary Regulation of the Independent Accountant Financial Advisor and Sworn-in Certified Public Accountant Law, "Signing, auditing and certifying declarations and notifications in violation of legal regulations and announced norms and standards, without the necessary care and diligence without intent, by members of the profession", the professional member was reprimanded.

As understood from this decision, an accountant is responsible for all statements made using his signature, title or name. While practicing his/her profession, he/she must pay attention to all the information, documents and declarations he/she provides. An accountant is also required to investigate whether the taxpayer's business is genuine. It should be remembered that the accountant is seen as part of the business and can be blamed for crimes committed by the business.

Another decision, similar to the others, concerns a violation of the Regulation on the Working Procedures and Principles of Certified Public Accountants and Sworn-in Certified Public Accountants. The member of the profession made an agreement with a person to bring clients for a fee of 100 TL per taxpayer, and the person brought taxpayers to him. Although regular payments were made for six months, the professional member terminated the employment contract because the payments were not received. However, during this period, the professional member gave his professional password to the

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

person who brought work to him. Thereupon, the person insured many people unbeknownst to the professional member as if they were working for the professional member and taxpayers. The professional member stated that he did not fill in the insurance entry and exit declarations and that he was not aware of them, and that he only submitted the VAT declarations of the relevant companies. However, the professional confirmed that he had an employment contract with the companies subject to the decision at the time of the events and that the companies were legally his taxpayers. The professional allowed someone else to use his office. This situation was considered as a violation of Article 9 of the Disciplinary Regulation of the Law on Certified Public Accountants and Sworn-in Certified Public Accountants, and it was decided to dismiss the professional member from the profession on the grounds that the professional member did not fulfill his responsibilities and acted against the law.

This decision is an indication that an accountant is fully responsible for the most important elements of his/her profession, such as his/her seal, signature authorization, password and working office. Under no circumstances should a practicing accountant allow his or her office to be used for activities outside the profession. The professional member is responsible for all accounting transactions made with his/her own password. As can be seen, failure to comply with these rules is so important that it may lead to one of the most severe penalties, which is dismissal from the profession.

In another decision, there are two professionals. A company learned that a person it considered to be its accountant was not in fact its accountant, and that this person was using the password and stamp of a professional accountant. The company executives similarly stated that the professional had prepared declarations that did not reflect their actual transactions and that according to these declarations they had made a revenue of 1,252,424.20 TL, which they said was too large a revenue figure to reflect the reality. On 19.09.2012, when the documents seized as a result of the search were examined, it was seen that the professional member had prepared false declarations for his taxpayers. Another allegation of the company owner was that the accountants made extra invoices for them, but they did not do any work. Upon the accusations of the company owner, the professional member subject to the decision stated that the other professional member was a former accountant, that he worked in his office, that he did not know the company in question, that he himself did not visit his office regularly and that he trusted the other professional member. The professional member added in his defense that the other professional member managed the work in the office, that he found all the taxpayers belonging to him and the other accountant, and that he gave him his password because he trusted him.

As a result, it was decided to dismiss the relevant professional member from the profession on the grounds that he did not use the powers granted to him, that he did not practice his profession himself but made his powers available to nonprofessionals permanently or temporarily, and that he allowed someone else to find clients for him.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

This decision clarifies that an accountant cannot temporarily or permanently delegate his authority and office to another accountant, no matter how much he understands accounting. A client filed a complaint after realizing that his accountant was not in fact his accountant and that he was collecting taxpayers by using the name of a real professional, thereby over-invoicing him and burdening him with extra tax burden by submitting false declarations. Subsequently, the real accountant's office was searched and it was determined that the complainant taxpayer was telling the truth in the documents seized.

The last decision is related to the fact that members of the accountancy profession cannot act contrary to the professional activities recognized by law. According to this decision, the professional member did not act in accordance with professional care and diligence while filling out declarations and issuing documents, and therefore, the person was sentenced to reprimand.

5. CONCLUSION

Every profession has responsibilities and the legal rules necessary to perform it. However, when it comes to the accountancy profession, it is seen that the consequences of not complying with these rules and rules are very high. Of course, the basis of this is that the profession carries out activities that concern the taxpayer, its employees, partners and investors, the government and society. If the profession is not practiced in accordance with the rules of law, it is possible that the accountant as well as the taxpayer and other financial responsible parties may face criminal sanctions. In addition, investors and shareholders will be misled, and plans for the future will cease to be realistic.

As a result of accounting errors and frauds, not only the taxpayer and its stakeholders but also the employees of the relevant organization will be affected. It is impossible to talk about the loyalty and trust of employees in an organization where accounting scandals occur. Likewise, customers and solution/business partners cannot be expected to trust the relevant organization. As a result of errors and/or frauds in accounting, the risk of the organization losing resources such as workforce and financial income in the short term is definitely increasing.

Another important body affected as a result of accounting fraud is, of course, the state and therefore the public. The state has to serve the public and needs resources to do so. Taxes are the most important financial resources of the state. For this reason, those who perform the accounting profession should always consider the public interest. A member of the profession should not forget that he/she is also responsible to the public and therefore must protect his/her independence under all circumstances.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

The above-mentioned sample decisions reveal that legal, ethical and moral rules must be adhered to in order for the accountancy profession to function. In this context, legal regulations should be updated according to the requirements of the profession and should meet the needs.

The most important factor in the accountancy profession is that individuals with professional competence should not have their professional transactions performed by others and should not share their passwords, stamps and offices with others. In the sample decisions, it is seen that accountants who commit these violations are banned from the profession. It is also noteworthy that reprimand is one of the most common types of punishment.

Apart from taxpayers, accountants have responsibilities towards their taxpayers' employees, shareholders, investors, the state, the international economy and society. In the study, it is noteworthy that in addition to personal reasons, the lack of legal audits and the lightness of sanctions are effective in not fulfilling their responsibilities. One of the most important results of the literature review is that when accountants decide to cheat on their own, they calculate the rate of getting caught and ease their conscience by thinking that "everyone does it anyway". In order to prevent this, the frequency of audits should be increased and attention should be paid to the establishment of mechanisms to supervise those who perform audits.

In the decisions analyzed in the study, it was observed that the most frequently committed offense was the issuance of false documents/statements as a result of trusting someone else by the professional members. As a result of the crimes committed by individuals to whom accountants give their passwords, members of the profession are punished. For this reason, it is very important to increase the level of awareness of professional members about sharing passwords, stamps and offices.

Another noteworthy detail is that accountants can be forced to make fraud by their employers. It would not be wrong to say that if the accountant's economic situation is bad, he/she may feel helpless about making fraud. In order to solve this problem, increasing the fees per taxpayer would be an important step.

REFERENCES

- Ahid, M. and Augustine, A. (2012). The Roles and Responsibilities of Management Accountants in the Era of Globalization. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 12(15), 42-53.
- Akalın, S. E. (2017). *TMS 8 Kapsamında Muhasebede Hata ve Hilelerin Tespiti ve Şirketlerin Bağımsız Denetim Raporlarının İncelenmesi*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi), Başkent Üniversitesi, Ankara.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

- Ambashe, M. and Alrawi, H. A. (2013). The Development of Accounting through the History. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*, 2(2), 95-100
- Bekçioğlu, S., Coşkun, A. ve Gümüş, U. T. (2013). "İşletmelerde Hile ve Yolsuzlukların Önlenmesinde Farklı Bir Yaklaşım: Adli Muhasebe." ("YOLSUZLUK, MUHASEBE HİLELERİ VE ÖRNEKLERİ (pdf) | Paperity") *Muhasebe ve Finansman Dergisi*, 59, 1-16.
- Can, A. V. ve Esen, S. (2010). "Osmanlı Muhasebe Sistemi ve 1530 Yılına İlişkin Yapılan Kayıtların Işığında "Bir Osmanlı Livası: Prizren"." ("Muhasebe ve Vergi Uygulamaları Dergisi » Makale - DergiPark") Erişim Adresi: http://www.mizanturk.com.tr/akademi/akademi_11420132224616.pdf Erişim Tarihi: 07.12.2022.
- Carmona, S., Ezzamel, M. and Gutierrez, F. (2004). Accounting History Research: Traditional and New Accounting History Perspectives. *Spanish Journal of Accounting History*, 1, 24-53
- Çalış, Y. E. ve Altınsoy, B. N. (2014). Yönetim Raporlama Sisteminde Sorumluluk Muhasebesi: Bir İnşaat İşletmesinin Maliyet Merkezine Yönelik Performans Analizi. *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 16(1), 29-44.
- Çankaya, F. ve Gerekan, B. (2009). Hile Denetçiliği Mesleği ve Sertifikalı Hile Denetçiliği Mesleki Standartları ve Ahlak Kuralları. ("Hile Denetçiliği Mesleği ve Sertifikalı Hile Denetçiliği Mesleki ...") *Muhasebe ve Denetime Bakış Dergisi*, 9, 93-108.
- Çitil, B. (2013). Vergi Hukukunda Mali Müşavirlerin Sorumluluğu. *TBB Dergisi*, 106, 345-356.
- Çürük, T. ve Tüm, K. (2011). Yeminli Mali Müşavirlerin Mesleki Sorumluluğuna İlişkin Sorunların Tespitine Yönelik Uygulamalı Bir Araştırma. *Ç.Ü. Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 20(3), 59-76.
- Demir, B. (2013). Kurumsal Sosyal Sorumluluk ve Muhasebe. *Eğitim ve Öğretim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(3), 225-233.
- Diyyaroğlu, M. (2010). *Muhasebeci Mali Müşavirlik Mesleki Sorumluluk Sigortalarında Sigortanın Temel Prensiplerine Aykırı Uygulamalar ve Bu Uygulamaların Sonuçları*. (Yüksek Lisans Tezi), Marmara Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
- Dönmez, A. ve Çavuşoğlu, K. (2015). "Hilelerin Ortaya Çıkarılması Bakımından Bağımsız Denetim ile Adli Muhasebenin Karşılaştırılması." ("Auditing Techniques to Minimize Accounting Related Fraud and Errors: A ...") *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 1(3), 34-67.
- Gomes, D., Carnegie, G. D., Napier, C. J., Parker, L. D. and West, B. (2011). Does Accounting History Matter? *Sage Journals, Accounting History*, 16(4), 389-402.
- İşgüden, B. ve Çabuk, A. (2006). Meslek Etiği ve Meslek Etiğinin Meslek Yaşamı Üzerindeki Etkileri. *Balıkesir Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 16, 59-86.
- Karakaş, D. (2016). *Türkiye’de Muhasebe Meslek Etiği Üzerine Bir İnceleme*. (Yüksek Lisans Tezi), Okan Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
- Karavardar, A. (2015). Hile Üçgeni Faktörlerinin Kanaat Fonksiyonları ile Tayini: Bir Türkiye Uygulaması. ("ÖZGEÇMİ - Giresun") *Marmara Üniversitesi Öneri Dergisi*, 11(43), 27-45.
- Kepekçi, C. (1995). Tasdikten Doğan Sorumluluk ve Denetim Riski. Erişim Adresi: <http://dergiler.ankara.edu.tr/dergiler/42/468/5397.pdf> Erişim Tarihi: 07.12.2022.
- Köse, Y. ve Ertan S. (2016). Türkiye’de Bağımsız Denetçilik ve Bağımsız Denetçinin Sorumluluğu. *Uluslararası Yönetim İktisat ve Yönetim Dergisi*, Özel Sayı, 304-305.
- Küçük, E. ve Uzay, Ş. (2009). Hileli Finansal Raporlamanın Oluşumu ve Doğurduğu Sorunlar. Erişim Adresi: http://iibf.erciyes.edu.tr/akademi/mh/suzay/Hileli_Raporlama.pdf Erişim Tarihi: 07.12.2022.
- Mojgan, S. (2012). Examining the Role of Responsibility Accounting in Organizational Structure. *American Academic & Scholarly Research Journal*, 4(5), 1-6.
- Okay, S. (2011). *Muhasebe Hata ve Hilelerinin Meslek Etiği Açısından İncelenmesi*. (Yüksek Lisans Tezi), Karamanoğlu Mehmet Bey Üniversitesi, Karaman.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

- Özyürek, H. (2012). Muhasebe Meslek Mensuplarının Taşınması Gereken Nitelikler. *Hukuk ve İktisat Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 4(1), 139-148.
- Saçaklı, Y. (2011). "Adli Muhasebecilik Perspektifinde Türkiye'deki Üniversitelerde Muhasebe Denetimi Eğitimi ve Öneriler." ("Muhasebe ve Vergi Uygulamaları Dergisi » Makale » A ... - DergiPark") (Yüksek Lisans Tezi), Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi, Afyon.
- Savaşan, F. (2006). Vergi Afları: Teori ve Türkiye Uygulamaları ("Vergi Barışı" Uygulama Sonuçları). ("Vergi afları: Teori ve Türkiye uygulamaları ("Vergi Barışı" uygulama ...)") *Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi, İ.İ.B.F. Dergisi*, VIII(1), 41-65.
- Şişmanoğlu, E. (2016). *Bağımsız Denetçinin Mesleki Yargısı ve Türkiye'de Bir Araştırma*. (Doktora Tezi), İstanbul Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
- Tilt, C. (2009). Corporate Responsibility, Accounting and Accountants, S.O. Idowu, W.L. Filho (eds.), *Professionals' Perspectives of Corporate Social II Responsibility*, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 2009.
- Ulusoy, Y. (2007). *Bağımsız Dış Denetim*. Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık.
- Yıldız, G. (2010). Muhasebe Mesleğinde Meslek Etiği ve Kayseri İl Merkezinde Bir Uygulama. *Erciyes Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 36, 155-178.
- Yılmaz, R. ve Kaya, M. (2014). Kurumsal Yönetim İlkelerinin Muhasebe Etik Kuralları İle İlişkisi, *İşletme Bilimi Dergisi*, 2(1), 17-35.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE